

Foreign Portfolio Investment and Rural Development in Nigeria

¹Williams, Handel Nachor (CPA) & ²Yisa, Joseph Majin (KSC, CNA)

^{1,2&3}Department of Accounting, Faculty of Management Sciences, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Rivers State, Nigeria

Corresponding Authors' Email: handel.williams@iaue.edu.ng¹, josephyisa@yahoo.com²

Abstract

The diversification of Nigeria's economy via higher foreign portfolio investment (FPI) may considerably enhance production capacity, which is crucial for rural development. This study analyses the influence of FPI on rural development progress in Nigeria. By improving access to financial services, FPI may indirectly assist rural development by equipping the workforce with vital skills and improve overall living circumstances. The independent variable in this study is foreign portfolio investment (FPI), measured by proxies such as foreign portfolio inflows and equity securities. The dependent variable is access to financial services, offering as a proxy for rural development. Using an ex-post facto research technique, the study evaluates time series data from 2005 to 2022, acquired from the Central Bank of Nigeria, World Bank indicators, and relevant scholarly publications. Multiple regression analysis is employed to analyze the effect of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The statistics suggest that foreign portfolio investment considerably impacts access to financial services and has a big impact on rural development, whereas equity securities have a moderate effect. It is necessary for the government of Nigeria to undertake policies that stable the macroeconomic environment in order to handle these concerns. The paper advises that financial institutions grow their presence in rural areas and offer personalized financial products and services. Additionally, enhancing regulatory frameworks to encourage foreign portfolio investment into rural enterprises and partnering with microfinance institutions will further boost financial inclusion and sustained economic development in Nigeria's rural regions.

Keywords: foreign portfolio investment, equity securities, rural developments, portfolio investment inflow

Introduction

Foreign portfolio investment (FPI) entails abroad investors depositing their money into financial assets like stocks, bonds, and mutual funds in a different country. Unlike foreign direct investment (FDI), where investors gain control over the assets or operations of a company, FPI involves passive ownership, meaning investors do not have a direct stake in the companies they invest in. This type of investment is generally characterized by its liquidity and

the ability to quickly buy or sell financial assets. Prospects for modest growth in Foreign portfolio investment remain possible in 2024, Referring to the loosening of financial restraints and the initiatives to boost investment via national laws and international agreements (World Investment Report 2024 /UNCTAD).

Foreign portfolio investment is inherently unstable, needing well-regulated financial markets to efficiently handle related risks. Furthermore, the financial system must actively identify and reduce these risks to guarantee the responsible and efficient allocation of both international and local capital flows. Economic growth and development rely on efficient financial intermediation and appropriate credit distribution. To maintain a healthy financial system, it is necessary to anticipate and manage business risks, while also guaranteeing resilience against economic shocks (FPI) flows to the US have been impacted by global economic conditions, geopolitical factors, and investor sentiment in recent years. Developing countries have faced challenges in attracting stable FPI inflows to support long-term growth (UNCTAD, 2024).

Portfolio investments are generally perceived less favourably compared to direct investments due to their liquidity, which allows for quick liquidation. This feature could contribute to the assumption that they are focused on short-term profits rather than long-term economic engagement. Typically, portfolio investments have shorter maturation dates than direct investments. Similar to other stock investments, foreign portfolio investors frequently expect rapid returns on their funds. Security market is typically an important indicator of a country's progressive growth (Iriobe, et al, 2018).

Portfolio investments are significantly more attainable for the typical investor, as they demand far less capital and research than direct investments. Additionally, the frequent trading of securities enhances the liquidity of portfolio assets, making them simpler to sell compared to direct investment. It has long been seen as a source of foreign private capital for all economies.

Its significance in preparing a nation for socioeconomic progress cannot be emphasized (Charles, et al., 2018).

A country's economy is vital in drawing international investment. Investors tend to favor a nation's financial assets when its economy is strong and expanding. In contrast, if the country experiences economic instability or recession, investors are prone to divest their holdings. Trade flows are of individuals and countries seeking to maximize their well-being and observing comparative advantage. Capital flows are of individual's and country's well-being by moving accumulated assets to more productive areas. In recent years, this grew to be a key element for worldwide wealth for funds to all economies, (Elekwa et al, 2020).

Moreover, the concentration of Foreign Portfolio Investment in urban areas and specific sectors, such as the oil and gas industry, may not directly benefit rural communities. The mass exodus of multinational companies from Nigeria in 2023, particularly in the manufacturing sector, could also have a detrimental effect on rural development, as these companies often provide employment and support local communities (Nigerian Economic Submit Group, 2023).

In conclusion, while foreign portfolio investment has considerably contributed to Nigeria's economic prosperity, its impact on rural development remains a complex issue. To ensure that the benefits of FPI are more evenly distributed, the government should focus on creating a more favorable investment climate, particularly in rural areas, and investing in basic infrastructure to attract foreign capital and support local communities.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the possible advantages of foreign portfolio investment (FPI) for Nigeria's economic growth and development, the inflow of foreign portfolio investment has been limited and

skewed towards short-term investments rather than long-term investments that could drive sustainable development, especially in rural areas. The Nigeria SDG Investor Map identifies investment opportunities that align with development needs and policy priorities. This mapping helps attract FPI into sectors that can generate both financial returns and positive social impacts, thus contributing to the SDGs (The United Nations Development Programme, 2024).

The Nigerian business environment is particularly unstable because to changeable government policies and a lack of transparency in government operations discouraging long-term foreign investors (Ehiedu, 2021). Portfolio investment inflows into Nigeria have been constrained by the early stages of growth in the country's capital and money markets, although recent expansion and improvement.

Foreign investment inflows into Nigeria are heavily skewed towards Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI) is separate from Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in several essential characteristics. FPI comprises investing in financial goods like shares and bonds, which frequently gives for better liquidity and fewer capital needs. In contrast, FDI refers to direct investments in physical assets or firms, involving a more large financial commitment and possibly a longer-term investment horizon suggesting the investment climate is anchored on the G20SFWG advocate for the development of policy frameworks that promote sustainable finance. Nigeria's alignment with these frameworks can help create a more stable and predictable investment environment, encouraging FPI that contributes to the SDGs (Obaro, et al., 2022).

Only a few states like Lagos and Abuja attracted investment inflows in 2024 Q1, indicating the need to make the business environment conducive to long-term investments across the country, including rural areas (Nigerian Economic Submit Group, 2023).

Unless there is a structural shift and sustained improvement in overall macroeconomic stability, there are limited chances that short-term foreign portfolio investors will reinvest their funds in Nigeria, especially in rural development projects. Addressing these issues is crucial for leveraging Foreign Portfolio Investment to drive inclusive and sustainable development across Nigeria.

Conceptual framework

Fig. 1: Showing the relationship between foreign portfolio investment and rural development in Nigeria.

Source: Researcher, (2024).

Research Objectives

The aim of this study is to thoroughly assess the relationship between foreign portfolio investment variables can provide capital to fund rural development services in Nigeria.

Research Question

The study seeks to answer: what is the effect of foreign portfolio investment on rural economic development in Nigeria?

Hypotheses

H₀: Foreign portfolio investment explanatory variables and access to financial services has no significant effect on rural development in Nigeria.

H₁: Foreign portfolio investment explanatory variables and access to financial services has a significant positive effect on rural development in Nigeria.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Conceptual Review

Foreign Portfolio Investment (predictor variable)

Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI) is a component of global capital flows, encompassing investments in financial assets like currencies, stocks, or bonds across international borders with the intention of earning returns. FPI may either boost or hinder the Indian economy and savings strategy with each short-term adjustment. The effect of Foreign Portfolio Investment is a significant component of global capital flows, involving the movement of financial assets across borders for profit (Kasthuri & Nirmala, 2019).

The impact of foreign portfolio investment varies depending on factors such as firm size, country creditworthiness, and property rights development. To attract Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI) countries should focus on developing strong regulatory structures (O & C, 2023), improving macroeconomic factors (Khayat, 2020), and enhancing corporate governance and transparency (Iriobe et al., 2018).

Equity Securities

Equity securities are financial instruments that symbolize ownership in a business, delivering shareholders with a claim to the firm's assets and income. They are a crucial component of investment portfolios for both individual and institutional investors, as they can significantly influence the risk-return profile of investments. Equity-linked securities contribute to improving the performance of optimal portfolios for most investors, regardless of investment

horizon, and are mainly used as substitutes for risk-free bonds rather than risky assets (Kang et al., 2019).

Equity securities are characterized by their potential for capital gains and dividends. They are influenced by market conditions, company performance, and broader economic factors. The valuation of equity securities is essential for investment analysis, as it helps determine their market price and the expected return on investment.

In conclusion, equity securities are vital to capital markets, enabling corporations to obtain funding while providing investors multiple options for ownership and profit sharing. Understanding the different types and characteristics of equity securities is crucial for effective investment management and portfolio diversification.

Foreign Portfolio Inflows

Foreign Portfolio Inflows refer to the movement of capital into a country through investments in its financial assets by foreign investors. These investments typically include stocks, bonds, mutual funds, and other financial instruments. Financial flows encompass several sorts of transactions, including stock exchanges, profits that are reinvested, and loans exchanged between connected businesses. In developing countries, foreign portfolio flows are vital for enhancing The expansion of financial markets plays a significant role in delivering foreign currency to fund current account deficits (Singhania & Saini, 2018; Leković M. 2018; Oluwatobi al., 2022).

Outward flows relate to transactions that boost the investment of investors from the reporting economy in overseas firms, which might occur via stock purchases or reinvested profits. This is countered by any activities that diminish their stake, such as share sales or loans obtained by the local investor from the foreign business. Conversely, inbound flows reflect transactions that

raise the investment of foreign investors in domestic firms, minus any transactions that lower their investment in those resident enterprises.

The substantial The infusion of foreign portfolio investments has posed numerous policy issues addressed by rising countries. These challenges include quick growth of credit, the formation of inflated asset valuations, unwelcome appreciation of local currencies, heightened external vulnerabilities, and the erosion of monetary policy independence (as explored by Koepke, 2019; Brodeur et al., 2020; Kuzman et al., 2022; Murdipi et al., 2023).

Moreover, as many developing countries often have a deficiency in savings relative to their investment needs, foreign portfolio flows aid fill this gap, hence promoting economic growth (Espelage et al, 1999; Gupta and Ahmed, 2020; Kábrt and Brůna, 2022; Verberi, et al., 2023).

Conclusively, Factors like the level of financial market development, macroeconomic conditions, and country-specific characteristics likely mediate the relationship between foreign portfolio inflows and growth.

Rural Development (Criterion Variable)

Rural development is a comprehensive approach focussing on strengthening the economic and social circumstances of rural areas, which often face unique challenges compared to urban regions. It encompasses various strategies and policies designed to enhance livelihoods, reduce poverty, and promote sustainable practices. It encompasses various aspects such as infrastructure development, economic diversification, and social empowerment (Rajović & Bulatović, 2019; Wang & Ma, 2023).

Rural development typically refers to initiatives that improve the living standards of people in rural areas, focusing on enhancing their economic, social, and environmental conditions. This includes agricultural development, but also extends to areas such as infrastructure, education,

and healthcare. Villages and towns play a crucial role as gathering places for rural industries and serve as bridges between urban and rural areas (Ma, & Wang, 2023).

Rural development is essential for achieving sustainable economic growth and social equity. By focusing on the unique needs of rural areas and fostering inclusive participation, it is possible to create vibrant, sustainable communities that contribute significantly to national and global economies. The integration of rural and urban development strategies is also critical to ensure balanced growth and mitigate the urban-rural divide. This integration can be supported through policies focusing on industrial development, infrastructure construction, and social undertakings (Wang & Ma, 2023; Zhou et al., 2023).

Access to Financial Services

Access to financial services is crucial for economic development, particularly in rural communities. It encompasses aiding people and businesses to access financial products and services like credit, savings, insurance, and payment alternatives systems. Digital technology innovation has significantly improved access to financial services for people with low incomes. Digital financial services, e-payments, and alternative finance models have successfully addressed traditional constraints such as geographical distance and administrative expenditures (Wanof, 2023).

However, the relationship between financial inclusion and stability is complicated. While access to payment and savings accounts typically has a neutral or positive affect on financial stability, credit

inclusion without proper consideration of borrowers' ability to repay can weaken financial stability (Feghali et al., 2021).

Theoretical Framework

Foreign portfolio investment can contribute to rural development in Nigeria through various channels. However, the relationship between FPI and rural development is complex and depends on several factors. Here is a theoretical framework for understanding this relationship:

Endogenous Growth Theory

Paul Romer's primary contribution to economic growth theory was to re-emphasize its significance at an era when macroeconomics was largely focused on inflation and unemployment. His 1983 dissertation and subsequent 1986 publication focused attention back to core questions of what determines the long-term growth rate of living standards. Romer presented a model where the long-term growth rate is set internally within the economy, rather than by external pressures. He also noted that due to externalities, the actual growth rate might be lower than the ideal rate. This research established the basis for what is now known as endogenous growth theory.

While the mechanics of Romer's work are definitely significant, one of its most crucial successes was restarting the study of economic development inside the economics profession. To underscore this effect, a search for the keywords "economic growth" and "endogenous growth theory" in Microsoft Academic showed that between 1973 and 1983, only 49 books on economic development got more than 1,000 citations. However, between 1986 and 1996, this quantity grew more than five-fold to 266 articles. This increase demonstrates the rekindled interest and active study in economic development fostered by Romer's contributions.

Relevance of theory

This theory posits that a well-functioning capital market can attract FPI, which in turn can lead to economic growth. In Nigeria, the development of the capital market has been linked to increased FPI, particularly in the bond and equity markets. This influx of capital can provide

necessary funding for rural development projects, such as infrastructure improvements and agricultural investments. Studies have shown that capital market indicators, such as market capitalization and turnover ratios, significantly influence FPI inflows, suggesting that enhancing market conditions can lead to more investment in rural areas.

Empirical Review

Nwosa et al. (2020) the study investigates the link between trade openness and Nigeria's unemployment rate from 1980 to 2018. It uses the auto-regressive distributed lag (ARDL) technique and finds that trade openness has a significant negative impact on unemployment. This suggests that trade openness provides employment opportunities, reducing unemployment. The study suggests that Nigeria needs conscious economic policies to encourage foreign private investment, which can boost investment volume and employment generation. Additionally, the government should explore new marketing areas for foreign investors to further boost employment generation.

Okafor et al., (2022) the study analyzed the impact of financial inclusion on the development of micro, small, and medium enterprises (MSMEs) in Nigeria using multiple linear regression. Data from the Central Bank of Nigeria's statistical bulletin (1981-2019) was used. The results showed that financial inclusion significantly benefits MSMEs, but challenges like distance to financial services, limited access points, and poor infrastructure hinder effective access. The study recommends expanding access points in rural areas and improving infrastructure, including a policy roadmap to extend financial services to unbanked and underserved regions using a geospatial map.

Ezeanyej and Maureen (2019), the study examines the impact of foreign portfolio investment on Nigeria's economic growth from 1986 to 2017. The research uses the Augmented Dickey-Fuller test, Johansen cointegration technique, and Error Correction Mechanism to analyze

variables such as net foreign portfolio investment, GDP, inflation rate, market capitalization, and trade openness. The results show that foreign portfolio investments have a positive impact on Nigeria's economic growth. The study recommends that the government implement policies to promote long-term growth of the capital market and economy, create a conducive business environment, provide constant power supply, good roads, and security of life and property. Additionally, the capital market should be further deepened through the introduction of derivatives.

Onuoha, et al., (2018), the research evaluated the causal and dynamic link between macroeconomic factors and Financial Performance Index (FPI) in West Africa from 1990 to 2016. The findings demonstrated that portfolio equity and bond do not substantially affect macroeconomic factors, implying underperformance of FPI. In the short and long term, portfolio stock and bond were minor in impacting real gross domestic product, suggesting underperformance. The research argues that the non-causality between FPI and macroeconomic factors might be due to weak economic activity in developing nations and the less developed character of the financial industry. This knowledge is significant for policy consequences.

Agbogun and Ehiedu (2022), this study examined the relationship between Foreign Portfolio Investment Flow (FPIF) and the Nigeria Stock Exchange (NSE) from 1981-2022. FPIF was represented by Equity Foreign Portfolio Investment (EFPI), Bond Foreign Portfolio Investment (BFPI), Money Market Instrument Foreign Portfolio Investment (MMIFPI), and Total Market Capitalization (TMKTC). The research used secondary data from NSE reports, CBN statistical Bulletins, World Development Indicators (WDI), and IMF World. The results showed that EFPI had a positive insignificant effect on TMKTC, while BFPI and MMIFPI had a significant effect. The study recommends a strong supervisory and regulatory structure to ensure strict

compliance with policies aimed at controlling indiscriminate capital transmission through EFPI.

Gap in literature

While there is substantial research on the relationship between foreign portfolio investment (FPI) and economic growth in Nigeria, there appears to be a gap in the literature regarding the specific impact of foreign portfolio investment on rural development. Most studies focus on the macroeconomic effects of foreign portfolio investment, such as its influence on Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth, stock market performance, and bond yields. However, the rural development implications of foreign portfolio investment have been largely overlooked.

Studies have found that foreign portfolio investment has a significant positive impact on stock market returns in Nigeria, but the bond market has received less attention. Foreign portfolio investment inflows into Nigeria surged to a 4-year high of \$3.4 billion in Q1 2024, driven by improved investor confidence in the country's reforms (NESG, 2024). Capital market development, particularly stock market capitalization, has been shown to positively influence foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria (Araoye, 2021).

However, none of the studies directly examine how foreign portfolio investment impacts rural development outcomes such as poverty reduction, infrastructure, employment, and economic diversification in rural areas. Given that a large portion of Nigeria's population resides in rural areas and relies on agriculture, understanding the rural development implications of foreign portfolio investment is crucial for policymakers seeking to promote inclusive growth.

In conclusion, while the macroeconomic effects of foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria have been well-studied, the specific impact on rural development remains an understudied area. Future research should investigate channels through which foreign portfolio investment could

promote development in Nigeria's rural communities, such as investment in rural infrastructure, agricultural productivity, and small and medium enterprises. Examining cross-country comparisons with other emerging economies could also yield valuable insights. Filling this gap in the literature would provide a more comprehensive understanding of the development implications of foreign portfolio investment in Nigeria.

Methodology

To ascertain that, the study investigates the connection between foreign portfolio investment and rural development wherein an ex-post facto research methodology was applied. To determine whether or not the variables were stationary, Statistical techniques such as Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) regression can be employed to estimate the coefficients and assess the significance of each variable in influencing rural development. The interaction between FPI and rural development can be modeled to understand how foreign investments can be leveraged to enhance economic growth in rural areas. This write-up outlines a potential model specification that incorporates various economic indicators and variables relevant to Nigeria's rural development. In order to determine whether or not there is a connection that exists throughout the course of time between the variables, the researchers carried out a bound test. The Central Bank of Nigeria(CBN) statistical bulletin between the year 2005-2022 served as the source for the secondary data that was included into the research.

Research Design

The study will employ a quantitative research design using time series data. The analysis will be conducted at the national level, focusing on Nigeria.

Model Specification

Dependent Variable

Rural Development Index (RDI): This could be a composite index measuring various aspects of rural development, including access to financial services.

Independent Variables

Foreign Portfolio Investment (FPI): Measured in USD, representing the total inflow of foreign investments into the equity and bond markets of Nigeria.

Equity Securities (ES): A measure of the overall economic output, which can influence and reflect rural development.

Model Formulation

The model could be structured as follows:

$$RDI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ESS + \beta_2 FPI + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots 1$$

The mathematical model could be symbolically expressed as;

$$RDI = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ESS + \beta_2 FPI + \epsilon \dots\dots\dots 2$$

Where:

β_0 is the intercept,

$\beta_1, \beta_2 \dots \beta_1, \beta_2$ are the coefficients representing the relationship between each independent variable and the dependent variable.

ϵ is the error term.

Logarithmic transformations are often used as a convenient approach for turning highly skewed data into a distribution that is comparable to normalcy (Kenneth, 2011). This is accomplished via the use of the natural logarithm.

Results and Interpretation

Model Summary^b

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Durbin-Watson
1	.673 ^a	.452	.374	1.11670	1.393

a. Predictors: (Constant), LOG_ESS, LOG_FPI

b. Dependent Variable: LOG_AFS

The R value of 0.673 suggests a moderate positive correlation between the predictors (LOG_ESS, LOG_FPI) and the dependent variable (LOG_AFS). The R Square value of 0.452 means that about 45.2% of the variability in LOG_AFS is explained by this model. Adjusted R Square value of 0.374, indicating that after adjusting for the number of predictors, about 37.4% of the variance in LOG_AFS is accounted for by the model. Standard Error value of 1.11670 indicates a relatively low deviation of observed values from the line of best fit, suggesting a good model fit. Durbin-Watson Statistic value of 1.393 suggests no significant autocorrelation in the residuals.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	14.421	2	7.211	5.782	.015 ^b
	Residual	17.458	14	1.247		
	Total	31.880	16			

a. Dependent Variable: LOG_AFS

b. Predictors: (Constant), LOG_ESS, LOG_FPI

The significance value (Sig.) of 0.015 indicates that the regression model is statistically significant at the 0.05 level. This means that the predictors (LOG_ESS and LOG_FPI) have a significant relationship with the dependent variable (LOG_AFS).

Coefficients

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
1	(Constant)	-11.461	6.699		-1.711	.109		
	LOG_FPI	1.909	.594	.636	3.213	.006	.998	1.002
	LOG_ESS	-.239	.250	-.189	-.954	.356	.998	1.002

a. Dependent Variable: LOG_AFS

LOG_FPI B Value shows 1.909 with Significance of 0.006 clearly stating a statistically significant position implying a positive and significant relationship with LOG_AFS. This suggests that an increase in foreign portfolio investment is associated with an increase in access

to financial success. LOG_ESS B Value shows -0.239 and indicating 0.356 (not statistically significant) implying no significant relationship with LOG_AFS. This indicates that changes in equities securities do not have a statistically significant impact on access to financial success in this model. Since there is no significant multicollinearity, the positive impact of LOG_FPI on LOG_AFS can be trusted as both LOG_FPI and LOG_ESS have VIF values of 1.002, indicating no significant multicollinearity issues. This means the regression coefficients for these predictors are reliable and can be interpreted with confidence.

Hypothesis

H₀: Foreign portfolio investment explanatory variables and Access to Financial Services has no significant effect on rural development in Nigeria.

Equity Securities(ESS) has a significant effect on access to financial services (LOG_AFS) showing result of p-value for LOG_ESS as 0.354, which is greater than the common significance level of 0.05. Decision: Fail to reject the null hypothesis (which states that LOG_ESS has no effect) and do not accept the alternative hypothesis that Equity Securities significantly affects access to financial services.

H₁: Foreign portfolio investment explanatory variables and Access to Financial Services has a significant positive effect on rural development in Nigeria.

Foreign portfolio investment has a significant effect on access to financial services (LOG_AFS) as result shows p-value for LOG_FPI is 0.006, which is less than the common significance level of 0.05. Decision: Reject the null hypothesis (which states that LOG_FPI has no effect) and accept the alternative hypothesis that foreign portfolio investment significantly affects access to financial services.

Findings and Conclusion

The analysis highlights the significant role of foreign portfolio investment in enhancing access to financial services in rural Nigeria. While equity securities is vital for overall development, its direct impact on financial services in agriculture may require further investigation. By focusing on attracting foreign investments and integrating them with improvements in essential services, stakeholders can foster sustainable rural development. Policies aimed at improving these services can lead to better financial services and overall economic growth in rural areas. Supporting financial literacy and access to credit for rural populace can boost productivity and sustainability as market interventions can help maintain consistent rural revenues, encourage sustainable agricultural practices.

Conclusion

The proposed model aims to quantify the impact of Foreign Portfolio Investment on rural development in Nigeria, considering various economic factors. By analyzing these relationships, policymakers can formulate strategies that enhance the effectiveness of FPI in promoting sustainable rural development. Further empirical research is necessary to validate the model and refine the variables based on real-world data and trends.

Further Research

It may be beneficial to conduct further research to explore other variables and their interactions. For instance, examining the role of local governance, community initiatives, and environmental sustainability could provide a more comprehensive understanding of rural development.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations includes:

Firstly, financing infrastructural deficits for FPI has the potential to significantly contribute to addressing Nigeria's infrastructural deficits. Studies indicate that FPI can enhance funding for long-term projects, which are essential for rural development, by providing necessary capital to finance infrastructure improvements such as roads, schools, and healthcare facilities.

Secondly, economic growth impact is critical as research shows a complex relationship between FPI and economic growth in Nigeria. While some studies suggest a positive correlation between FPI and economic growth, others indicate that FPI alone does not significantly impact growth, particularly when considering factors like inflation and exchange rates. This underscores the need for favorable policies that enhance the investment climate to attract FPI, which could subsequently support rural development initiatives.

Thirdly, capital market development as Nigeria's capital markets is crucial for attracting FPI. Effective regulation and transparency in the financial markets can enhance investor confidence, leading to increased FPI inflows. This is particularly relevant for rural areas, where improved capital markets can facilitate investments that directly benefit local economies.

Fourthly, Short-term versus Long-term Investments using the current trend in Nigeria shows a skew towards short-term investments, which may not be conducive to sustainable rural development. A shift towards attracting long-term FPI could provide the stability needed for significant rural development projects, as these investments are generally less volatile and more reliable for funding essential services.

Finally, governmental policies plays a pivotal role in shaping the FPI landscape. Implementing favorable trade policies and creating a stable macroeconomic environment can encourage more foreign investors to commit to long-term projects in rural areas. This is vital for achieving broader economic goals, including poverty reduction and improved living standards in rural communities.

In summary, studying the relevance of foreign portfolio investment in the context of rural development in Nigeria is essential for understanding how to leverage external capital for sustainable growth. It highlights the need for effective policies that can attract long-term investments, thereby facilitating infrastructure development and enhancing economic opportunities in rural areas.

References

- Araoye, F. E. (2021). *Economic development and foreign capital investment inflow in Nigeria* (pp. 80–94). Accounting and Taxation Review. https://www.zbw.eu/econis-archiv/bitstream/11159/6198/1/1769388389_0.pdf
- Brodeur, A., Clark, A. E., Fleche, S., & Powdthavee, N. (2021). COVID-19, lockdowns and well-being: Evidence from Google Trends. *Journal of Public Economics*, 193, 104346. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpubeco.2020.104346>
- CHARLES, D., NENBEE, S. G., & KRAMA, I. J. (2018). Public Investment in the Social Sector and Employment Generation in Nigeria, 1980-2016. *Greener Journal of Social Sciences*, 8(1), 001-011. <https://doi.org/10.15580/gjss.2018.1.122617182>
- Dawazhaxi, Zhou, W., Yu, W., Yao, Y., & Jing, C. (2023). Understanding the indirect impacts of urbanization on vegetation growth using the Continuum of Urbanity framework. *Science of the Total Environment*, 899, 165693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2023.165693>
- ELEKWA, P. , ANIEBO, C., & Christopher, D. I. K. E. (2020). *Foreign Portfolio Investment Creates Positive Spillovers, But How?.* Tsuniversity.edu.ng; JALINGO JOURNAL OF SOCIAL AND MANAGEMENT SCIENCES. <http://oer.tsuniversity.edu.ng/index.php/jjsms/issue/view/5>

- Espelage, D. L., Bosworth, K., & Simon, T. R. (2001). Short-Term Stability and Prospective Correlates of Bullying in Middle-School Students: An Examination of Potential Demographic, Psychosocial, and Environmental Influences. *Violence and Victims*, 16(4), 411–426. <https://doi.org/10.1891/0886-6708.16.4.411>
- Ezeanyej, C., & Maureen, I. (2019). Foreign Portfolio Investment on Economic Growth of Nigeria: An Impact Analysis. In *International Journal of Academic Management Science Research* (pp. 24–36). International Journal of Academic Management Science Research (IJAMSR). <http://ijeais.org/wp-content/uploads/2019/03/IJAMSR190304.pdf>
- Feghali, K., Mora, N., & Nassif, P. (2021). Financial Inclusion, Bank Market Structure, and Financial Stability: International Evidence. *The Quarterly Review of Economics and Finance*, 80(6). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.qref.2021.01.007>
- Gupta, K., & Ahmed, S. (2020). Determinants of foreign portfolio flows to Indian debt market. *Journal of Indian Business Research*, ahead-of-print(ahead-of-print). <https://doi.org/10.1108/jibr-01-2019-0024>
- Hassan Khayat, S. (2020). Determinants of International Foreign Portfolio Investment Flows to GCC Countries: An Empirical Evidence. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 15(10), 51. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ijbm.v15n10p51>
- Hussain, M., & Goswami, B. (2022). Sector Specific Determinants of Foreign Portfolio Investment Inflows in India: A Panel ARDL Approach. *Global Business Review*, 097215092211372. <https://doi.org/10.1177/09721509221137204>
- Kábrt, T., & Brúna, K. (2022). Asymmetric effects of foreign capital on income inequality: The case of the Post-China 16 countries. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 76(C), 613–626). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eap.2022.08.025>

- Kang, S. H., Maitra, D., Dash, S. R., & Brooks, R. (2019). Dynamic spillovers and connectedness between stock, commodities, bonds, and VIX markets. *Pacific-Basin Finance Journal*, 58, 101221. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pacfin.2019.101221>
- Kasthuri, K., & Nirmala, M. (2019). Foreign Portfolio Investment And Macroeconomic Factors In India. *International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering*, 8(12), 2056–2058. <https://doi.org/10.35940/ijitee.l3259.1081219>
- Koepke, R. (2018). WHAT DRIVES CAPITAL FLOWS TO EMERGING MARKETS? A SURVEY OF THE EMPIRICAL LITERATURE. *Journal of Economic Surveys*, 33(2), 516–540. <https://doi.org/10.1111/joes.12273>
- Kuzman, T., Lazarevic, J., & Nedeljkovic, M. (2021). Capital flows liberalisation and macroprudential policies: The effects on credit cycles in emerging economies. *Economic Analysis and Policy*, 73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eap.2021.12.010>
- Leković, M. (2018). Investment diversification as a strategy for reducing investment risk. *Ekonomski Horizonti*, 20(2), 173–187. <https://doi.org/10.5937/ekonhor1802173l>
- Ma, W., & Wang, X. (2020). Internet Use, Sustainable Agricultural Practices and Rural Incomes: Evidence from China*. *Australian Journal of Agricultural and Resource Economics*, 64(4). <https://doi.org/10.1111/1467-8489.12390>
- Muazu, A., Abdullahi, I. O., & Alhassan, A. S. (2024). EFFECT OF FOREIGN INVESTMENT INFLOWS ON CAPITAL MARKET PERFORMANCE IN NIGERIA. *International Journal of Accounting, Finance and Business*, 9(55). <https://academicinspired.com/ijafb/article/view/849>
- NESG. (2023). *The Nigerian Economic Summit Group | Blog*. Nesgroup.org; Effect on rural development on Employment. <https://www.nesgroup.org/blog>
- Nigerian Economic Summit Group, N. (2024). *The Nigerian Economic Summit Group | Foreign Investment Inflows into Nigeria Surged to a 4-year High in 2024Q1*.

Nesgroup.org. <https://nesgroup.org/blog/Foreign-Investment-Inflows-into-Nigeria-Surged-to-a-4-year-High-in-2024Q1>

Nwosa, P., Keji, S., Adegboyo, S., & Fasina, O. (2020). TRADE OPENNESS AND UNEMPLOYMENT RATE IN NIGERIA. *Oradea Journal of Business and Economics*, 5(2), 52–62. <https://doi.org/10.47535/1991ojbe111>

Obaro, V. C., Onuorah, A. C., Evesi, H. O., & Ehiedu, V. C. (2022). Diversification and the Performance of Quoted Banks in Nigeria. *Quest Journal of Research in Business and Management*, 10(10), 46–54.

Oghenekparobo Agbogun, & Ehiedu, V. (2022). Trade Policy Drivers and Economic Performance of Opec Member States. *ResearchGate*, 6(8), 109–118. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374779572_Trade_Policy_Drivers_and_Economic_Performance_of_Opec_Member_States

Okolie, J. O., & Ehiedu, V. C. (2023). FOREIGN PORTFOLIO INVESTMENT FLOW (FPIF) AND NIGERIAN STOCK EXCHANGE (NSE). *International Journal of Management & Entrepreneurship Research*, 5(2), 85–98. <https://doi.org/10.51594/ijmer.v5i2.441>

Oluwatobi, F. O., Babatunde, O. O., & Adegbite, E. O. (2020). *Drivers of Foreign Private Investment Inflows in Emerging Market: Evidence from Nigeria*. ACTA UNIVERSITATIS DANUBIUS . google Scholar

Onuoha, F. C., Okonkwo, I. C., Okoro, P., & Okere, K. (2018). The causal relationship between Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) and the macro-economy of selected west African countries: Panel ARDL/Granger Causality Analysis. *African Research Review*, 12(1), 140. <https://doi.org/10.4314/afrrrev.v12i1.15>

Rafiq Murdipi, Ahmad Zubaidi Baharumshah, & Siong Hook Law. (2023). Portfolio capital flows and economic growth: Do institutional factors matter? *Research in*

International Business and Finance, 66, 102019–102019.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ribaf.2023.102019>

Rajović, G., & Bulatović, J. (2016). Rural Roads - Issues and Development: Overview.

JOURNAL of MANAGEMENT and ACCOUNTING STUDIES, 4(04), 70–77.

<https://doi.org/10.24200/jmas.vol4iss04pp70-77>

Saini, N., & Singhania, M. (2018). Determinants of FDI in developed and developing countries: a quantitative analysis using GMM. *Journal of Economic Studies*, 45(2), 348–382. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jes-07-2016-0138>

Stanley Osinachi Okafor, Henry Onyebuchi Ejelonu, & Chukwuebuka Godwin Onyekwere. (2022). Financial Inclusion And Micro, Small And Medium Enterprises (Msmes) Development In Nigeria. *International Journal of Innovation in Engineering*, 2(2), 42–53. <https://doi.org/10.59615/ijie.2.2.42>

UNCTAD. (2024, June 20). *World Investment Report 2024*. UNCTAD.

<https://unctad.org/publication/world-investment-report-2024>

Verberi, C., Yasar, S., & Sugoza, I. H. (2023). Capital liberalization, growth and moral hazard: Lessons from the global financial crisis. *International Review of Financial Analysis*, 90, 102901. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.irfa.2023.102901>